

TEACHING THE FUNCTIONAL ROLE OF METAPHORS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE WORKS THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL COOPERATION

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the study of the role of metaphor in the English language. The purpose of the work is to determine the purpose of metaphors and determine the function of metaphors in literary works of the English language. The relevance of this work is due to the ambiguity of the representation of metaphor as a linguistic unit. When used in speech, it carries a certain linguistic load. It is used in works of art to give the statement an emotionally expressive tone.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена обучению метафоры в английском языке посредством педагогики сотрудничества. Цель статьи – определить функцию метафор в литературных произведениях английского языка. Актуальность данной статьи заключается в неоднозначности репрезентации метафоры как языковой единицы. При использовании в речи оно несет определенную лингвистическую нагрузку. Она используется в художественных произведениях для придания высказыванию эмоционально-экспрессивного оттенка.*

Each language has its own characteristics and uniqueness. Mostly, it can be seen in the usage of metaphors, phraseologisms and other stylistic devices that can be difficult to understand for people learning the language. Metaphors are used to make a piece of art more vivid and colourful and learners of languages should know their meanings and application.

Translating metaphors is a complicated task where translator should convey the significance by preserving the meaning of a word.

Some linguists argue that metaphors violate the author's intent and make translation difficult. Since a metaphor is a word or expression used in a figurative meaning, which is based on a comparison of an object or phenomenon with some other on the basis of their common characteristic. Learners of the languages, unfortunately, do not always understand this hidden meaning. They have to examine the entire context to understand the implicit content of the metaphor.

A huge number of works by scientists are devoted to the problems of studying metaphors.

According to V.N. Telia, metaphor is predominantly considered “as a stylistic means or artistic technique, less often - as a means of nomination, even less often - as a way of creating a linguistic picture of the world”.

The most common point of view is convincingly formulated by L.V. Kulchitskaya, according to which the linguistic metaphor is secondary in relation to the cognitive one, since “it exists due to the presence of a person’s brain, thinking and speech”, and since “in addition to language and speech, other forms of objectification of metaphor are behavior, visual arts, gestures - all those phenomena by which one can judge the presence of metaphor in conceptual thinking and, more deeply, the action of the mechanism of cognitive metaphor”

Thus, Johnson and J. Lakoff argued that “metaphor permeates our everyday life, and not only language, but also thought and action ... our ordinary conceptual system in terms of which we think and act is metaphorical in nature.”

John Rogers Searle pointed out that the basis of the theory of metaphor is the idea that consciousness is an abstract mechanism that processes raw data, its internal structure correlates with and therefore depends on perceived objects and phenomena.

The study of metaphor follows a natural path of development within the framework of the dominance of the cognitive approach - from the study within the framework of the theory of tropes, stylistics, rhetoric and lexicological studies of secondary nominations to analysis of cognitive processes based on metaphorical structures.

The ellipticity of the metaphor is updated, leading to the need to restore its “hidden” components, based on the identification of which cognitive models of the metaphor are created. To do this, linguists can resort to the use of non-linguistic research methods associated with structures such as frame, gestalt.

There are metaphors in the English language that should not be translated literally. For example:

1. “To give someone a hand” - this does not mean to give a hand, it means “to help someone.”
2. “You’re building castles in the air” - does not mean that you literally build castles in the air, it means - you’re making unrealistic plans
3. “I could eat a horse” - does not mean that someone can really eat a horse, it means - I am very hungry
4. “My brother was boiling mad”- this does not mean at all that he has gone crazy, he is just angry.
5. “The elephant in the room” – does not mean that there is a real elephant in the room, it means - a topic that everyone is thinking about but nobody is talking about.

There are several types of metaphors in literature: standard, implied, visual, extended, mixed and dead. Each of them carries certain features.

Standard metaphors are metaphors where the comparison between two entities (things - objects, people, concepts) is obvious and direct. It implies that one idea is another. Standard metaphors can also be called as direct or explicit metaphors. For example, “The snow was a white blanket warming the forest ground”, “She’s the light of my life”.

Implied metaphors compare two dissimilar objects, without revealing them directly, but imply the subtle change in wording. For example, “The singer howled some high notes to wrap up her concert.” The implied metaphor here compares the woman to a wolf, a creature unable to be a real musician.

Visual metaphors use visual means in order to show the connection between two dissimilar entities. These types of metaphors are commonly used by advertisers and artists. For example, “The way ice cream commercials show molten chocolate is intended to evoke the same sensual pleasure as experienced when eating the ice cream”.

Visual metaphors extend beyond two-dimensionality into architecture and product design. For instance, Frank Lloyd Wright’s design of the Johnson Wax Headquarters includes giant mushroom-shaped pillars to evoke the sense that buildings are part of the natural world.

Extended metaphors - comparison that occurs over multiple lines, pages, chapters, or an entire work. Its use allows writers to develop complex comparisons and foster insightful connections.

The extended metaphor also doesn't work to make a serious point or construct an argument, since being a comparison between two incompatible realms it will inherently contain critical fallacies. Extended metaphor should be used for humor or creative expression only.

In "Hope is the Thing with Feathers," Emily Dickinson uses an extended metaphor to compare hope with a perched bird that never stops singing: Hope is the thing with feathers That perches in the soul, And sings the tune - without words, And never stops at all, And the sweetest in the gale is heard; And sore must be the storm That could abash the little bird That kept so many warm. I've heard it in the chilliest land, And on the strangest sea; Yet, never, in extremity, It asked a crumb of me.

Mixed metaphors combine two incompatible metaphors that create an illogical comparison. there is no correlation between the compared things. For example, "He has been burning the midnight oil at both ends".

Dead metaphors occur when the original meaning of the comparison is losing or changing their initial meaning over time due to excessive repetition or a semantic shift. People can understand this types of metaphors not knowing their original meanings, therefore, they are viewed more literally in a reader's mind. For example, phrase "falling in love," which was once a metaphor equating love with the process of falling – risky and sometimes resulting in injury.

Metaphor is a linguistic unit that carries a linguistic emphasis. Therefore, it is appropriate to highlight the main functions of metaphor.

Nominative function. It is used when naming any objects or phenomena in an expressive form. For example, the English name Jerry means "ruler of the spear." Nominative functions are more clearly depicted at the interlingual level.

Genre function. When metaphorical properties are involved in the creation of a genre. For example, a riddle: I have no spur to prick the sides of my intent (horse).

Game function. This function is often used if it is expressed in a saying, proverb, etc. For example: grow big but do not be like noodles.

Conspiracy function. It is presented in the text in a hidden sense: the fever of the soul, wasted in the desert.

If you replace a metaphor with an ordinary word in its literal meaning, the speech will not have such a vivid character. In order for speech to be rich and beautiful, the line between a metaphor and a new word should be seen. However, scientists have not yet reached a consensus on the relationship between metaphor and extended meaning.

Vivid metaphors are found in the works of English writers. For example, in A. Huxley's work "Point Counter Point," the metaphor: "the emotion was always flowing" implicitly expresses the emotional state of a character whose mood fluctuates from loving to hostile feelings: "One way or the other, the emotion was always flowing. There were hardly any intervals of comfortably slack water. The tide was always running."

Metaphors can be a reference to any work. For example, the metaphor of the same author: "funeral baked meats" (baked meat for a funeral) in the statement "Monday's funeral baked meats did service for Tuesday's wedding" resembles lines from Hamlet and implicitly implies readiness for the funeral of the father.

In addition, authors often resort to the use of metaphors to express a satirical effect. Zoometaphors, namely comparisons of humans with animals, serve to create an atmosphere of comedy, while the author highlights the characteristics of animals, thereby emphasizing the positive or negative qualities of humans. For example, K. Boyle, in his work "On the Run" uses the metaphor: "soft pink tide of pigs", compares a person with an animal, which makes a person's appearance more rich and bright and funny: "As the train stopped a soft pink tide of pigs rose out of the station-yard".

Often authors personify their characters and endow animals with human qualities. Thus, in the work of W. Shakespeare "Hamlet" in the statement of the hero Horatio: The cock, that is the trumpet to the morn, / Doth with his lofty and shrill sounding throat / Awake the god of day) the author uses the metaphor: "the cock is trumpet to the morn" as a personification, where he compares the rooster to the trumpeter of the dawn, who with his high and ringing throat awakens the day god from his sleep.

T. Williams in the work "Suddenly Last Summer" discusses the meaning of life and uses the metaphor: "trails of debris" (ashes), where a person is compared to dust: "Most people's lives—what are they but trails of debris, each day more debris . . . with nothing to clean it all up but, finally, death."

Based on the analysis of the literary works of English writers, we come to the conclusion that metaphors are an integral part of any work. They decorate speech and give the text emotionality, expressiveness.

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